

SPATIO-TEMPORAL EFFECTS OF LAND USE AND LAND COVER (LULC) CHANGES AND DYNAMICS OF NORMALIZED VEGETATION INDEX IN EBOH FOREST (40 YEARS) AT EPOCHS OF 20 YEARS INTERVAL USING GEOSPATIAL TECHNIQUE

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Keywords

spatio-temporal, land use, land cover, geospatial, vegetation.

Abstract: This study assessed the extent and dynamics of forest degradation in Eboh Forest located in Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State, over a forty-year period (1984-2024). The study integrated geospatial techniques with field-based ecological assessments to evaluate land use and land cover (LULU) changes. Landsat satellite images for 1984, 2004, and 2024 were processed and analyzed using Geographic Information System (GIS) tools, while the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was employed to assess vegetation greenness and productivity. Results revealed substantial changes in LULU patterns in Eboh forest, characterized by a decline in dense vegetation and a corresponding expansion of farmland, built-up areas, and road infrastructure. Although Forest experienced higher rates of early vegetation loss, it showed signs of partial recovery in later year, as reflected by increasing NDVI values. Eboh Forest exhibited persistent anthropogenic pressure with slower vegetation recovery. The study concluded that Eboh the forest retain some ecological functionality, continued human pressure threatens their long-term sustainability. Integrated conservation strategies, continuous geospatial monitoring, and community-based management are recommended to ensure effective forest restoration and sustainable use.

Introduction

Land use land cover deals on how the land is been utilized for specific period of time, (LULC) represent critical indicators of the interactions between human activities and the natural environment. Land cover refers to the biophysical attributes of the Earth's surface, such as vegetation, water bodies, and built-up areas, whereas land use describes the manner in which land is utilized by humans for economic, social, and cultural purposes. Changes in LULC

have profound impacts on ecosystem services, biodiversity, hydrological cycles, and regional as well as global climate systems.

In recent decades, rapid urbanization, population growth, agricultural expansion, and infrastructural development have intensified LULC changes worldwide. These transformations often lead to environmental degradation, land fragmentation, and resource depletion if not properly managed. Consequently, accurate and timely information

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on the spatial and temporal dynamics of LULC is essential for sustainable land management, environmental monitoring, and informed policy-making.

Traditional methods of LULC mapping, including ground surveys and manual cartographic techniques, are often labor-intensive, time-consuming, and limited in spatial extent. In contrast, geospatial techniques particularly Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) provide efficient, cost-effective, and reliable means for monitoring land surface changes over large areas and extended time periods. Advances in satellite sensor technology have improved spatial, spectral, and temporal resolution, enabling detailed classification and change detection of LULC patterns.

The integration of RS and GIS facilitates the extraction, analysis, and visualization of spatial data, thereby enhancing the understanding of LULC dynamics and their driving forces. These techniques have been widely applied in urban growth analysis, agricultural land monitoring, deforestation assessment, and environmental impact studies. Despite their widespread application, region-specific LULC assessments remain necessary due to varying socio-economic and environmental conditions.

Therefore, this study aims to assess land use and land cover patterns and changes using geospatial techniques, with the objective of quantifying spatial distribution, detecting temporal changes, and providing scientifically robust information to support sustainable land-use planning and environmental management.

Statement of Problem

Anthropogenic activities contribute greatly to deforestation and biodiversity loss which Nigeria is not exempted. Till date, most forest in the country have not received considerable attention to provide in-debt understanding of the factors responsible for their degradation. There is a drought of geospatial data on the trend and pattern of some Forests in Ahoada East Local Government Area. This therefore justifies this study to determine the changes in the Forest for a period of forty years.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to determine the spatio-temporal effects of land use land cover changes in Eboh Forest at 40 years epochs of 20 years interval using geospatial technique. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the changes in Eboh Forest for a period of 40 years (1984- 2024) s
2. To determine the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) of the Forest

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

This study was carried out in Eboh Forest in Ahoada East Local Government Area (LGA) of Rivers State (Fig. 1). Eboh Forest cut across Ula-Upata and Ula- Ehuda Road .Ahoada East LGA is one of the 23 local government areas in Rivers State, Nigeria. It has a total population of 166,324 (NPC, 2006). Ahoada East LGA shares boundary with Ahoada West, Emohua, Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Areas (Fig. 3). The area has a year-round high temperature of mean daily and annual values of 36 °C and 28 °C respectively (Idris, et al., 2024) characteristic of the tropical region. It experiences about 2400 – 2500 mm mean

annual rainfall (Udom, et al., 2024) with double peaks of rainfall at the months of July and September (Udom et al., 2024). The area is also characterized by high relative humidity and sunshine. Ahoada East LGA has two distinct seasons: the dry season and rainy season. The dry season lasts from November to March while the rainy season is from April to October. As stated by Idris et al. (2024), rainfall in this region during the rainy season follows a sequential increase from March to October

before decreasing in the dry season months of November to February.

The climatic characteristics described above occur due to the interaction of warm- moist South-West trade wind from the Atlantic Ocean which transports its moisture content to the coastal areas of Niger Delta and dry-warm North-East trade wind from the hinterland (Dimuna, et al., 2024). Thus, Ahoada East LGA has a warm-wet climate.

**Area showing the Study Locations
Composite Map of Nigeria, Rivers State and Ahoada East Local Government**

Composite of Eboh Forest Showing Sample Plot Locations

GIS Methods of Data Collection and Analysis

Data Collection

Land use/land cover (LULC) classification is a fundamental aspect of this study and the base of the spatio-temporal analysis of forest change. In the study, classification approach involved a geospatial workflow that includes image acquisition, pre-processing, enhancement, data training, supervised classification and accuracy estimation.

Image Acquisition and Preprocessing

The Landsat images of the target years: 1984; 2004 and 2024 were downloaded from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) database. The images were selected at the same season with less than 10% cloud cover, to eliminate the influences of seasonal changes

and cloud cover effects that may cause atmospheric interferences, Table 1 shows the features of the landsat images employed. Image pre-processing was carried out to ensure temporal comparability and spectral integrity in all the study periods. Radiometric correction was carried out to convert digital number (DN) values to top-of-atmosphere (TOA) reflectance, and atmospheric correction was achieved with the Dark Object Subtraction (DOS) technique (Chavez, 1996). Geometric correction was carried out to ensure spatial consistency whereby all the datasets were aligned to the WGS 1984 and Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) Zone 32N datum.

Table 1: Features of the Landsat Images Used

	1984	2004	2024
Scene ID	LT05_L1TP_188056_198 4042_02_T1	LE07_L1TP_188056_200 40108_02_T1	LC08_L1TP_188056_202401 07_20240111_02_T1
Sensor ID	"TM"	"L7_ETM"	"L8_OLI_TIRS"

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Space Craft ID	Landsat 5	Landsat 7	Landsat 8
Spatial Resolution	30m	30m	30m
Cloud Cover	10%	10%	10%
Acquisition Date	1984-04-20	2004-01-08	2024-01-07
Datum	"WGS84"	"WGS84"	"WGS84"
UTM	32N	32N	32N

Flow chart of LULC Classification Analysis

$$\text{Overall Accuracy} = \left(\frac{\sum CCP}{\sum TNP} \right) \times 100 \text{ -----}$$

--- (1)

Where CCP = the main diagonal for all correctly classified pixels

TNP = Total number of pixels

The off-diagonals represent the misclassified pixels (Otukey and Blaschke 2010).

- Kappa Coefficient (K) - measures the degree of agreement between the classification and ground-truth. Many studies including Ayanlade (2015) and Ubaekwe et al. (2024) have described Kappa coefficient as a better option for assessing the accuracy of LULC classification due to its ability to analyze single

error matrix and also compare the discrepancies between diverse error matrices. It is estimated as described in the equation below:

$$\text{Kappa (K)} = \frac{Q \sum_{i=1}^r x_{ii} - \sum_{i=1}^r (n_{i \cdot} k_i)}{Q^2 - \sum_{i=1}^r (n_{i \cdot} k_i)} \text{ -----}$$

(2)

Where K = Kappa coefficient value, Q = total number of observations in the matrix; r = the number of rows in the error matrix; x_{ii} = number of observations in column i and row i; n_i = total observations in row i; k_i = total observations in column i.

According to Jensen (2005), Lilles and et al. (2004) and Wang et al. (2010), Kappa coefficient values greater than 80% indicates strong agreement between the classification and reference data (high classification performance), Kappa values between 40 and

80% indicates moderate agreement between the classification and reference data (moderate classification performance), while Kappa values less than 40% indicates poor and weak agreement between the classification and reference data (poor classification performance)

Area Coverage, Net Change, and Annual Rate of Change of Each LULC Class

- The area coverage of each LULC classes were calculated in arc toolbox using Map algebra to calculate the spatial extent of each pixel indicating a particular LULC class. This approach has been generally used by many scholars including (Lambin et al. 2003, Demissie et al., 2017 and Ubaekweet al. 2021).
- The Net change of LULC class between two periods 1984 – 2004 and 2004 – 2024 were estimated by determining the differences between two successive study periods. The percentage change and the annual rate of change in hectare were calculated using the expression according to (Abate, 2011; Demissie et al., 2017).

$$\text{Net Change}_i = A_{t2,i} - A_{t1,i} \text{ -----}$$

Equation (3)

Where:

$A_{t2,i}$ = Area coverage of LULC type i at time t2

$A_{t1,i}$ = Area coverage of LULC type i at time t1

Note that a positive outcome indicates gain in the LULC class area, whereas a negative result indicates loss in the LULC class area.

$$\text{ARC}_{\text{Yr}}^{\text{ha}} = \frac{A_2 - A_1}{t} \text{ ----- Equation (4)}$$

$$\% \text{ARC}_{\text{Forest}} = \frac{\text{ARC}_i}{\text{TOF}} \times 100$$

Where ARC = Annual Rate of change in LULC class, A_1 = Area coverage of LULC class at first study year, A_2 = Area coverage of LULC class at second study year

TOF = Total Area coverage of the forest

Results and Discussion

The status of Eboh Forest for 1984, 2004 and 2024 are presented in Figures 5 and 6 respectively. Eboh Forest reserve was characterized by dense vegetation, sparse vegetation farmland and built-up across the study periods.

**Status of Eboh Forest Reserve across the Study Periods
Land Use and Land Cover Classification Accuracy**

The accuracies of the land use and land cover classifications within the study periods are

presented in Tables 2 to 4. The percentage Kappa coefficients of Eboh Forest reserve for 1984, 2004 and 2024 classifications were 89%, 95% and 96% respectively.

Accuracy Assessment of LULC Classification of Eboh Forest for 1984

LULC Class	Dense Veg	Sparse Veg	Built-up	Farmland	Total	Commission	User's Accuracy
Dense Veg	52	2	2	0	56.00	0.07	0.93
Sparse Veg	1	45	3	2	51.00	0.12	0.88
Built-up	1	2	49	0	52.00	0.06	0.94
Farmland	3	2	0	50	55.00	0.09	0.91
Total	57.00	51	54.00	52.00	214		
Omission	0.09	0.12	0.09	0.04			
Producer's Accuracy	0.91	0.88	0.91	0.96			
Over all accuracy	0.92						
P(r)	0.25						
Kappa	0.89						
Kappa (%)	89.00						

Accuracy Assessment of LULC Classification of Eboh Forest for 2024

LULC Class	Dense Veg	Sparse Veg	Built-up	Farmland	Total	Commission	User's Accuracy
Dense Veg	52	0	1	1	54	0.04	0.96
Sparse Veg	0	49	0	2	51	0.04	0.96
Built-up	1	0	47	0	48	0.02	0.98
Farmland	0	1	0	49	50	0.02	0.98
Total	53	50	48	52	203		
Omission	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.06			
Producer's Accuracy	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.94			
Over all accuracy	0.97						
P(r)	0.25						
Kappa	0.96						
Kappa (%)	96.00						

Area Coverage of Each Land Use and

vegetation increased from 5.48ha in 1984 to

Land Cover Class in Eboh Forest Reserve

The area coverage of each land use and land cover class in Eboh Forest reserve for 1984, 2004 and 2024 are presented in Figure 7. Eboh Forest reserve was dominated by dense vegetation (28.29ha) in 1984, which decreased to 24.04ha in 2004 and 22.65ha in 2024. Sparse

vegetation increased from 5.48ha in 1984 to 6.12ha in 2004 and later decreased to 3.18ha in 2024. Built-up and farmland exhibited increasing trend, from 3.00ha and 1.36ha in 1984 to 4.22ha and 3.75ha in 2004; and subsequently 5.44ha and 6.86ha in 2024 respectively.

Area Coverage of Each LULC Class in Eboh Forest across the study Periods

Normalize Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

The spatio-temporal distribution of the Normalize Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) of Eboh Forest for the periods of 1984, 2004 and 2024 are presented in Figures 8 and 9,

respectively. Eboh Forest increased from minimum and maximum values of 0.3823 and 0.5897 in 1984 to 0.3803 and 0.7007 in 2024 respectively

Figure: NDVI of Eboh Forest Reserve in 1984, 2004 and 2024

NDVI of Eboh in 1984, 2004 and 2024

Discussion

The status of Eboh Forest was characterized by dense vegetation, sparse vegetation, farmland, road and built-up reflects the status of most forests in Nigeria. Ubakwe et al (2022), and Duru et al (2024) recorded a comparable status in Oba Hills forest Reserves. Osun State, Finima Nature Park, River State and Afi forest reserve cross Rivers State, respectively.

The accuracies of the land use and land cover classifications within the study periods shows that the percentage kappa coefficient of Eboh Forest reserves for 1984, 2004 and 2024 classifications were 89%, 95% and 96% respectively;

The area coverage of each land use land cover class in Eboh Forest reserve was dominated by dense vegetation (28.29 ha) in 1984. Built-up which decreased to 24.04ha in 2004 and 22.65ha in 2024. Sparse vegetation increased from 5.48ha in 1984 to 6.12ha in 2024 and later decrease to 3.18ha in 2024. Built-up and farm land, exhibited increasing trend, from 3.00ha

and 1.36ha in 1984 to 4.22ha and 3.75ha in 2004 and subsequently 5.44ha and 6.86ha in 2024 respectively.

Net changes in LULC types with the study periods in Eboh Forest reserve show dense vegetation lost 4.25ha between 1984 and 2004 and further lost 1.39ha between 2004 and 2024. Sparse vegetation also lost 0.64ha between 1984 and 2004 and regained 2.94ha between 2004 and 2024. Built-up and farmland farmed 1.23ha and 2.38ha between 1984 and 2004; and further expanded to gain 1.21 ha and 3.11ha between 2004 and 2024 respectively

Conclusions

The study examined the spatio-temporal effects of land use and land cover (LULC) changes in Eboh Forest over four decades (1984–2024).The forest was characterized by dense vegetation, sparse vegetation, farmland, and built-up/road areas, with dense vegetation being the predominant land cover type. NDVI values were moderate and showed an increasing trend, indicating gradual improvements in vegetation greenness and photosynthetic activity.

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